

A MODIFICATION OF THE GUARESCHI PYRIDINE SYNTHESIS. PART I.

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A method for the Guareschi pyridine synthesis originated in the observation that when a mixture of cyanoacetic ester and ethylideneacetoacetic ester was treated with ammonia, a dicyano-imide was obtained together with a little dihydrocollidine dicarboxylic ester and a third substance of unknown constitution (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1897, I, 927; Quenda, *ibid.*, 903). The formation of these compounds is explained by a preceding hydrolysis of the ethylidene derivative. With benzaldehyde, the esters and ammonia, Guareschi obtained a compound melting at 222-23°. Later on (*ibid.*, 1907, I, 332) he observed that the product in this case also was a complex mixture, one component of which, (m.p. 225-26°) was definitely characterised to be the open-chain amide (I), while a second, (m.p. 226-27°) was claimed to be oxyppyridine (II), derived from (I) by loss of water and hydrogen.

The compound (m.p. 222-23°) is not mentioned in this later work. It will be noticed that all the above three compounds have very close melting points and it appears necessary to reinvestigate the matter to determine their constitution and to see if they are all really different. At the outset, it was thought advisable to reduce the complex nature of Guareschi's reaction by coupling the four reactants in pairs and to treat the resulting benzylideneacetoacetic ester and cyanoacetamide with a more suitable condensing agent. Thus with a few drops of diethylamine, the condensation proceeded very smoothly and deposited crystals, m. p. 222-23°, in 68% yield. No other compound could be obtained by varying the conditions. Guareschi's experiment in itself was then repeated in aqueous solution and it was found that only two products could be isolated, one, the same as before, m.p. 222-23°, and the other, the open-chain amide (I), m.p. 225-26°, the former or the latter preponderating according as the tempera-

ture was maintained low with ice or not. It is doubtful if the pyridone (II) is formed at all. The amide having been definitely characterised, the former compound was taken up for elucidation of its constitution. Analysis showed it to be an addition product ($C_{16}H_{18}O_4N_2$) but its properties could not be reconciled to the open-chain structure (I), for it did not evolve any ammonia with boiling caustic soda but dissolved to give a yellow solution to be reprecipitated by acids, redissolving in slight excess of the latter and reappearing on allowing the solution to stand. There is no doubt that the primary reaction is an addition between the two molecules, for on boiling with dilute hydrochloric acid for three hours the substance dissolved and the solution after evaporation and extraction with ether, gives an acid, m.p. 82° . This was identified to be β -phenyl- γ -acetylbutyric acid (Knoevenagel and Fries, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 762).

In the literature a parallel case has been recorded (Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 322). Allen and Scarrow (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1934, 11, 395) condensed cyanoacetamide with unsaturated ketones and obtained additive products with similar properties. To such compounds they have attributed a cyclic aldol structure due to tautomerisation between the amido and carbonyl groups in 1 : 6 position. The compound in question is also probably best represented by a ring structure, for in addition to the anomalous properties of its amido group, the absence of any carbonyl in it was established beyond doubt. It did not form any semicarbazone, was oxidised to a gum with sodium hypobromite solution and to benzoic acid with chromic acid. It failed to react with Grignard reagent in ether suspension or boiling pyridine solution. It, therefore, may be represented as (III) but it differs in many of its reactions from the similar ring

(III)

(IV)

compounds of Barat (*loc. cit.*) and of Allen and Scarrow (*loc. cit.*). Thus with dimethyl sulphate two methyl groups are introduced but the product is a monomethoxy derivative and is presumably represented by (IV). The aldol structure, on dehydration, was expected to pass readily into Guareschi's

compound (II). In acetic anhydride suspension, addition of a few drops of strong sulphuric acid caused it to warm up and go rapidly into solution, but it was attended with considerable decomposition of material with evolution of carbon dioxide even though it was cooled in ice. Replacement of the acid by the pyridine gave better result when heated under reflux for two hours and the product on analysis was found to agree with the formula $C_{14}H_{17}O_3N$ (V) derived from the parent substance by withdrawal of the cyano and carbe-thoxy groups, followed by acetylation (*cf.* Allen and Scarrow, *loc. cit.*). This structure explains its insolubility in caustic soda. Alcoholic sulphuric acid, hot caustic soda or even barium hydroxide ruptures the ring.

It is indeed very surprising to note that all attempts to dehydrate (III) with phosphorus pentachloride, pentoxide or hydrogen chloride in dry chloroform solution met with failure until with a controlled action of phosphorus trichloride in boiling benzene, the compound (VI) was obtained.

Like the parent substance, it dissolves in alkali with a yellow colour. It melts at 142° and is different from Guareschi's pyridone (II). That during dehydration, hydrogen atoms are not eliminated is indicated by its ready transformation into (VII) with dimethyl sulphate.

The ring formation by tautomerisation of amide hydrogen atom seemed very interesting and such abnormal reactivity may be attributed to the fact that in (I), the amide group acquires certain mobility due to its position next to carbonyl and the very close proximity of a second carbonyl of the aceto-acetic ester residue, being in the sixth position with regard to it. It would

thus appear that the non-existence of one of these negative groups would render it incapable of forming the ring. To test this view cyanoacetamide was conveniently replaced by the dinitriles of Mayer (aminoarylacrylonitriles) which are capable of reacting in the tautomeric form $R C (: N H) \cdot CH_2CN$. These appeared to be far less reactive towards the unsaturated ester and if condensation could be effected, the products were not analogous in all cases. Before a definite conclusion may be drawn, the results require a more critical examination and will be communicated shortly.

In the above condensations benzylidene-acetoacetic ester was next replaced by benzylidene-cyanoacetic ester. Cyanoacetamide readily combined in presence of diethylamine and needle shaped crystals (m. p. 266-68°) began to separate within an hour. On allowing the mixture to stand at room temperature for several days, it was noticed that the needles were entirely replaced by small grains, m. p. 245°. Both the substances in amyl alcohol give a deep brown colouration with ferric chloride. The latter is a dicyano-oxyppyridone (IX), already obtained by Guareschi (*Chem. Zentr.* 1899, II, 118) and by Day and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1473) by different methods. Its sodio derivative is the only product when sodium ethoxide is employed as the condensing agent. The former compound passes into the latter quickly on boiling with acids. The analytical data agree with the formula $C_{17}H_{20}O_2N_4$ and it evolves with alkali a gas having an ammoniacal smell but not tarnishing Nessler's solution. Since the diones are known to possess marked acidic properties it appears to be a diethylammonium salt (VIII) produced according to the following scheme.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

Condensation of Cyanoacetamide with Benzylidene-acetoacetic Ester : Formation of 5-Cyano-6-keto-2-oxy-2-methyl-3-carbethoxy-4-phenylpiperidine.—Cyanoacetamide (0.8 g) and benzylidene acetoacetic ester (2.2 g.) (Knoevenagel, *Ber.*, 1896, 17, 2) were dissolved in sufficient warm alcohol so that the amide did not crystallise out on cooling. A few drops of diethylamine were added when the solution warmed up considerably and the colour gradually darkened to dirty brown. After keeping overnight the crystals separating were collected and washed with alcohol. Colourless needles from alcohol m. p. 222-23°, yield 1.7 g. It is soluble in acetone and in hot caustic soda with a yellow colour. (Found : C, 63.54; H, 6.24; N, 9.53. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires C, 63.57; H, 5.96; N, 9.27 per cent).

Hydrolysis : Formation of β -Phenyl- γ -acetylbutyric Acid.—A suspension of the substance in dilute hydrochloric acid was boiled under reflux and in 2 hours a perfect solution was obtained. On cooling it became milky and after another 2 hours a small quantity of oil separated. On allowing to stand overnight, preferably in an ice-chest, clusters of needles were obtained. The mother liquor on evaporation and extraction with ether gives a second crop. The total quantity was crystallised from water, m. p. 82°. (Found : C, 69.70; H, 6.99. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 69.90; H, 6.79 per cent).

Methylation : Formation of 5-Cyano-6-methoxy-2-oxy-2 : 5-dimethyl-3-carbethoxy-4-phenyltetrahydropyridine.—On adding dimethyl sulphate to the warm solution of the substance in caustic soda (10%) a gummy mass separated. On allowing it to stand in water for 2 days it solidified. It was twice crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 162°. (Found : C, 65.23; H, 6.52; OMe, 9.61. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires C, 65.45; H, 6.66; OMe, 9.4 per cent).

Reaction with Acetic Anhydride.—The substance was suspended in acetic anhydride with a drop of pyridine and boiled. Prolonged heating darkened the colour and on pouring into water and allowing to stand, it separated in the form of needles. It crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 145-46°. (Found : C, 68.25; H, 6.82; N, 6.11. $C_{14}H_{17}O_3N$ requires C, 68.01; H, 6.88; N, 5.74 per cent).

Treatment with Phosphorus Trichloride : Formation of 5-Cyano-6-oxy-3-carbethoxy-2-methyl-4-phenyl-4 : 5-dihydropyridine.—The substance in benzene suspension was heated for about 2 hours on a water-bath with phosphorus trichloride. A gummy mass was obtained from which the product could be isolated with difficulty in extremely poor yield. The operation was much more successful when the mixture after boiling was evaporated,

treated with water, extracted with ether, the extract repeatedly washed and evaporated. The residue was a pale yellow solid which crystallised from water containing acetic acid, m. p. 142° . (Found: C, 67'81; H, 5'88; N, 10'10. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires C, 67'60; H, 5'6; N, 9'86 per cent).

The *Methylation* of the above compound with dimethyl sulphate produced an oil which solidified after 2 days. It crystallised from methyl alcohol, m. p. 149° . (Found: C, 69'52; H, 6'44; N, 9'25; OMe, 10'11. $C_{18}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 69'23; H, 6'41; N, 8'97; OMe, 9'93 per cent).

Condensation of Cyanoacetamide with Benzylidene-cyanoacetic Ester:
 (i) *Formation of Diethyl ammonium salt of 3:5-Dicyano-2:6-diketo-4-phenyl-piperidine.*—The solution of the amide (0'8 g) and the ester (2 g.) in absolute alcohol was treated with diethylamine. After keeping overnight at room temperature it set to a mass of white needles. It is almost insoluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, etc. It crystallises from amyl alcohol or pyridine in flat lancet like needles, m. p. 268° ; yield 1'4 g. It dissolves in warm water and on adding concentrated hydrochloric acid to the cooled solution a white mass is obtained, m. p. 245° (see below). (Found: C, 65'12; H, 6'2; N, 17'8. $C_{17}H_{20}O_2N_4$ requires C, 65'38; H, 6'4; N, 17'94 per cent).

(ii) *Formation of 3:5-Dicyano-6-hydroxy-4-phenyl- $\Delta^{8:9}$ -dihydro-2-pyridone.*—If in the above condensation, the mixture was allowed to stand for 4-5 days, the needles separating were gradually entirely replaced by pale greenish cubes, m. p. 245° . It dissolves in boiling water and the aqueous solution on acidification precipitates the substance as a white shining mass. (Found: C, 65'58; H, 3'40; N, 17'92. $C_{18}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires C, 65'8; H, 2'9; N, 17'7 per cent).